

DOIP Endorsement Request

Version 1.1

FDO Forum Endorsement Request 17 October 2022

Current Version: [PED-DOIPEndorsement-1.0-20220608](#)

<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1me0L8C5yDe39cYP1Sxud4Y10hxhphOimLB-K-KgHQUk/edit#>

Previous Version:

<https://docs.google.com/document/d/1HGXB2WsqHd5VDAFLA0iXwAnKCU7JqLT86XhTQSHfFFs/edit>

Editors:

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Abstract

The DOIP Version 2.0 as released by the DONA Foundation¹ [1] is endorsed as an important contribution to the FDO Forum specification stack. The DOIP interfacing protocol specifies how clients can interact with DOs independent of the technology used by a DOIP server and independent of the data organization chosen. Since FDOs are a subset of DOs, restricted by the requirement to be FAIR compliant and thus machine actionable, DOIP will also work for FDOs as specified by the FDO Forum.

DOIP is an important component for implementation of FDOs using the DO approach. It has been tested by several institutions, as the Demonstrator paper from the eING WG has shown [2], there is a tested Software Development Kit [3], and there is an open-source reference implementation [4].

¹ Handle: 0.DOIP/DOIPV2.0

Status of this document

This document is an Endorsement Request ER-V1.0 proposed by the TSIG WG after a month of commenting without severe objections. The DOIP standard will be maintained by the DONA Foundation. The DOIP Specifications have been applied by several institutions successfully, i.e., currently there are no requests for changes to DOIP. This Endorsement Request will be turned to an Endorsed Recommendation of the FDO Forum when all comments have been resolved and the SC has accepted the endorsement request.

Acknowledgments

This document is based on the work of the DONA Foundation plus several developers who have applied and tested DOIP successfully (see Demonstrator Paper [2]).

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1. DOIP Endorsement Rational

The major task of the FDO Forum is to specify FDOs in detail and to provide a comprehensive set of specifications enabling interested parties to carry out implementation work. The overall FDO specifications will need to offer space for different realizations such as those being worked on by the Linked Data community relying on the Web-protocol stack or by the Digital Object community relying on specifications worked out by Kahn & Wilensky [5] and later by the RDA

DFT group² [6]. Users are not just interested in abstract specifications, but also want to understand whether the basis for concrete implementation work is available.

Since DOIP is an essential base component to make the DO approach to FDOs work, the FDO Forum needs to check DOIP on its completeness, its compliance with the emerging FDO specifications and, in case of positive results, add it to its “portfolio” of usable realizations. To carry out the checks it makes use of the process as described in its document process standard [7].

This diagram indicates the layers within the FDO portfolio. At the top are its specifications that need to allow for different realizations. At the bottom are different protocol stacks which also need to be based on specifications enabling checks by machines.

This document describes completeness and FDO compliance and refers to practical implementations showing that it is running code that can be used.

2. DOIP

The DOIP interface Protocol has been specified as one key element of the Digital Object Architecture as suggested by the DONA Foundation. The definition of a DO by DONA and by the FDO Forum are nearly identical with the exception that the FDO Forum requires all Digital Objects to be FAIR compliant and thus support machine actionability. This implies that all FDOs are DOs, but not all DOs that will exist will be FDOs.

The DOIP protocol specifies a standard and unified way for clients to interact with Digital Objects independent of the technology being used by the DO server and independent of the way data is being organized. Since FDOs are a subset of DOs, DOIP can also be applied to interact with FDOs.

DOIP makes extensive use of PIDs³, which are compliant with the ITU X.1255 standard [8], and supports enhanced security options through use of a PKI infrastructure where required. It makes use of TLS as a minimum transport protocol but can also be layered on top of HTTP as transport layer.

² It should be noted that the result of the RDA DFT group has been approved as a European Standard and is referred to in the EOSC Interoperability Framework [9].

³ PIDs in the sense of globally unique resolvable persistent identifiers.

This diagram indicates the typical interaction between a client and a server both making use of DOIP request and response packages. It also indicates the situation which will be typical for many repositories, for example, which are not yet FAIR compliant and where the DOIP server acts as proxy.

This document is not meant to describe the features of DOIP in detail. For details we refer to the DOIP V2.0 Specification document.

3. FDO Compliance

Although the FDO Requirement Specifications are still being worked out in detail, we can state that DOIP is compliant when used in accordance with the actual versions of the FDO specification documents in progress:

- FDO Requirement Specifications
- FDO Machine Actionability
- FDO Configuration Types
- FDO PID Profiles and Attributes
- FDO FDO Granularity

Since FDOs are a subset of DOs DOIP is also applicable to FDOs. Achieving FDO compliance requires more than DOIP and full compliance is thus left to system designers. DOIP is an abstract protocol allowing for a variety of usage scenarios, both with current technology and with technologies which may emerge in the future.

4. Use of DOIP

DOIP has been applied by a number of institutions. A software development kit and a reference implementation are both available.

SDK: The DOIP Software Kit is open source and can be downloaded and used.

Cordra: A digital object server which combines repository, registry, and identifier services, also provides a DOIP reference implementation. The software is freely available.

The Demonstrator paper[2] provided by the FDO Form illustrates how some institutions have successfully applied DOIP. A few implementations can be referenced:

- CNRI-GWDG: exchange of DOs between repositories using different technologies and data organizations, one using a native DOIP server and the second a DOIP proxy to couple a non-FAIR with a FAIR repository
- Indiana University: In a comprehensive workflow solution FDOs are created systematically and DOIP is used to interact with the created FDOs stored in a repository.
- DiSSCo: In the biodiversity domain, the Cordra software is being used to store the Digital Specimens consisting of core data and many distributed data sources. For the interaction with the Fair Digital Objects stored in the Cordra software DOIP is used.

Therefore, we conclude that the DOIP V2.0 is a ready to use component for the FDO Forum intentions.

5. Changes from previous versions

Version	who	when	changes
1.0	editors	7.6.2022	- a few stylistic changes have been made - some references were added - changed the referencing to FDOF documents to refer to the actual version
1.1	Editors	17.10.2022	- no further comments were made

6. References

[1] DOIP V2: Handle: <http://hdl.handle.net/0.DOIP/DOIPV2.0>

[2] Demonstrator Paper: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5872645>).

[3] DOIP SDK: <https://www.dona.net/specsandsoftware#block-digitalobjectinterfaceprotocol>

[4] Cordra: <https://www.cordra.org/documentation/client/doip-java.html>

[5] Robert Kahn, Robert Wilensky. A framework for distributed digital object services. 2006. International Journal on Digital Libraries (2006) 6(2): 115–123.
<https://doi.org/10.1007/s00799-005-0128-x>

[6] RDA DFT: <http://hdl.handle.net/11304/5d760a3e-991d-11e5-9bb4-2b0aad496318>

[7] DOc Proc Standard:

https://docs.google.com/document/d/1IPNBBROjEoZ6TftrtdqcMa3Q2G27PoC_/edit

[8] ITU X.1255: <https://www.itu.int/rec/T-REC-X.1255-201309-I>

[9] EOSC Interop Framework: <https://doi.org/10.2777/620649>